

Appendix E Interview Procedure

E.1 Purpose

The purpose of this interview is to

- Measure the completeness of the Traditional Knowledge Label (TKL) Ontology in comparison with the official TKL document with the help of interviewees
- Gather feedback on the current state of TKL ontology
- Get inspiration on how it can be used in the cultural domain.

E.2 Comparison

- **Informal and Formal questions**

- Informal: question form of statement sentences of TKL document
- Formal: SPARQL query

- **Informal and Formal classifications**

- Rules, Conditions, and ILC Wishes which are covered by TKL Label can be classified properly with ontology

E.3 Theme

Theme which revolves around Digital Sovereignty:

- Rules (How someone should interact with the item)
- Condition (What is the current condition of the item / What is the ideal condition of the item)
- Wish (What ILC or its members want to do with the item)

E.4 Entities Involved

1. ILC: The community, in this case Toba Batak people
2. Custodian: The current carer organization of the item, in this case Gallery or Museum
3. Public: People outside the ILC
4. Object: The item itself (originally called material in official TKL document)
 - Object/Material to Observe:
 - Tangible Intellectual Property of the Object
 - Intangible Intellectual Property of the Object

E.5 Language

Language of interview: Indonesia.

E.6 Interview Procedures (45–60 minutes)

Open Questions

Item 1: Ulos Ragidup

1. Show the Image
2. Could you tell me what you know about this type of item?
 - If needed, show the translated official information
3. Could you tell me your experience with this type of item?
4. How important is this Item to Toba Batak?
 - What is the traditional knowledge here?
 - What is the intellectual property here?
5. How do you feel about the use of this item for Exhibition in the New York Art Gallery?
6. How do you think this item needs to be treated?
7. What do you want to know more about this specific item?
 - Notes: Interviewer does not have to be answered, considered as competency question

Item 2: Pustaha

1. Show the Image
2. Could you tell me what you know about this type of item?
 - Show the translated official information
 - Show the content from official Wereld Museum website
3. Could you tell me your experience with this type of item?
 - If there's no personal experience
 -
 - Older generation's experience
 - Existing knowledge about this
4. How important is this Item to Toba Batak?
 - Contemporary Batak Toba?
 - (What do they know about) Batak Toba in the past?
 - What is the intellectual property here?
5. How do you feel about the use of this item for Exhibition in the Wereld Museum?
 - How do you think this item needs to be treated?
 - What do you want to know more about this specific item?
 - Does not have to be answered, as long as it can potentially be answered by both informal form (the real TKL document) and formal form (TKL Ontology)

TKL Ontology and TKL

Introduction to TKL Ontology

- Explain briefly the concept of Linked Open Data
 - Show graph data structure to easily visualize
- Show and Tell about the TKL ontology (General User Interface and the system)
 - Accommodate interviewee to interact with interface
 - Accommodate interviewee to interact with Protégé
 - Show the OntoGraph visualization
- Allow interviewee to inspect the system
- Ask how TKL Ontology can be used in cultural domain

Measuring Completeness

- Ask interviewee to make Competency Questions
- Try to explain feasibility with current system
 - Demonstrate

Inspire Application and Competency Question

- Explain briefly about TKL to keep the conversation focused
 - Introduce TKL concepts and purpose
 - Tell relevance to TKL Ontology
- Ask how TKL Ontology can be used in cultural domain
- More competency question

Comparison with Other ILC

- Explain how OMA tribe use TKL in their textile database
 - Similarity to the case of Ulos
- Ask how TKL Ontology can be used in cultural domain
- More competency question

Open Question Feedback

Ask **How** TKL Ontology can be used in digital world.